

A STUDY OF THE PERSONALITY TRAITS OF LYCOPODIUM CLAVATUM AND THEIR APPLICATION AND EFFECTIVENESS IN THE TREATMENT OF VARIOUS DISEASES IN CLINICAL PRACTICE

Dr. Uthpala Yaralagadda, *Post Graduate Scholar, Department of Homoeopathic Materia Medica, Bharati Vidyapeeth (deemed to be university), Homoeopathic Medical College & Hospital, Department of Post Graduate and Research Centre, Pune-Satara Road, Dhankawadi, Pune, India,411043.*

Dr. Vaishali V. Dolas, *Head of department, PG Guide, Department of Homoeopathic Materia Medica, Bharati Vidyapeeth (deemed to be university), Homoeopathic Medical College & Hospital, Department of Post Graduate and Research Centre, Pune-Satara Road, Dhankawadi, Pune, India,411043.*

ABSTRACT

Background- Mental states influence bodily organs through a combination of neural, hormonal, and immunological components. Motor neurons control voluntary movements through conscious brain commands, although these actions may sometimes be involuntary. The activation of corticosteroids during stress can suppress the immune system. Although the immune system protects the body from pathogens, exposure to stress and excitation is known to weaken its defenses against foreign bodies. The idea of personality traits dates back to Aristotle. Commonly, traits are seen as stable and directly influencing behaviour, although this view often involves circular reasoning. Scientific psychology aims to separate internal traits from observable behaviours, exploring their physiological, psychological, and social bases. **Methodology-** The study enrolled 30 patients from the outpatient department of Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Homoeopathic College & Research Centre, Katraj, Pune, of both sexes and various ages participated in this study. All 30 patients received prescriptions for 3 months of lycopodium clavatum, with follow-up visits scheduled for 15 days or as needed by the patient. Participants were assessed using the EPQR- A to measure personality traits before and after the homoeopathic intervention. The response to the intervention, including the main complaints, overall well-being and improvement in condition, was evaluated using “The Outcome In relation to impact on Daily Living (ORIDL)”. **Result-** The descriptive statistics from the study showed a notable decrease in the mean EPQR-A scores, dropping from 20.23 ± 1.04 before treatment to 13.06 ± 2.87 after treatment. The paired t-test demonstrated a T- statistic of 12.12 with a p-value of <0.001 , indicating a highly significant difference between pre- and post-treatment scores. The response to the intervention, including the main complaints, overall well-being and improvement in condition, was evaluated using “The Outcome In relation to impact on Daily Living (ORIDL)”. The chi-square test further supported these findings, showing a significant association between the levels of improvement in EPQR- A scores and overall patient conditions, with a chi-square statistic of 28.894 and a p- value of <0.001 . **Conclusion-** This study concludes that Lycopodium clavatum is effective, with significant improvements observed in personality traits and its related diseases. And, it showed significant results in treating various other diseases. The mental state reflects the essence of an individual and holds utmost importance in understanding the patient. It is believed that illnesses initially manifest on the mental plane before any physical changes occur. According to the principles of Hahnemann and Kent, mental and emotional symptoms take precedence over physical symptoms. This study shows the importance of mental generals in Homoeopathy which reflect the inner core of the individual.

KEYWORDS: Homoeopathy, Lycopodium, psychology, psychology

INTRODUCTION:

HUMAN MIND, HOW THE MENTAL HEALTH TRANSFORMS TO MENTAL ILLNESS:

This part of the body called the mind is where computation, comparison, analysis, creation, visualisation, planning, communication, and other functions are performed. They experience

alterations in consciousness and comprehension in this region of their body. A person is said to be in a mental health condition when they "realise their own potential, can manage with daily problems, can work successfully and fruitfully, and are able to contribute to their community." Any clinically significant impairment in cognition, emotion, or behaviour is indicative of a mental disease. It frequently leads to psychological anguish or impairment of functioning in critical areas.

The idea of personality traits dates back to Aristotle, who viewed traits like vanity and modesty as key to moral behaviour. Commonly, traits are seen as stable and directly influencing behaviour, although this view often involves circular reasoning. Scientific psychology aims to separate internal traits from observable behaviours, exploring their physiological, psychological, and social bases. The book emphasizes measuring and classifying traits, using methods like self-reports and observations. Traits are grouped into broader dimensions, with estimates ranging from three to thirty. Developing a theory of traits requires rigorous testing of hypotheses to understand their influence on behaviour, beyond family and shared environments. This research aims to study the personality traits of *Lycopodium clavatum* and their association with various diseases.

A person's distinctive and recognizable thought, emotions, and behaviour patterns that constitute their way of interacting with their social and physical surroundings are referred to as their personality. Adjectives like "extroverted" and "conscientious" are frequently used to describe personality traits when asked to characterize someone. What is the number of fundamental personality factors? There's no conclusive answer, not even after a rigorous analytical process. While Eysenck arrived at just three, Cattell arrived at sixteen. Various investigators have arrived at different conclusions. Many trait researchers are beginning to agree that the "Big Five" trait dimensions, which constitute the majority of personality traits, are "BIG FIVE". Eysenck suggests three such superfactors: extraversion (E), neuroticism (N), and psychoticism (P).

HOW STRESS AFFECTS HEALTH

The body's resources may be exhausted in an attempt to adjust to the ongoing stressor, leaving it more susceptible to disease. Allostatic load is the term used to describe the deterioration of the body caused by a persistent over- reaction of the physiological system to stress. Physical conditions like ulcers, high blood pressure, and heart disease can be brought on by prolonged stress. Additionally, it might weaken the immune system, making the body less able to repel germs and viruses that invade it. In fact, medical professionals believe that emotional stress is a major factor in over half of all medical issues. Emotions are thought to have a major role in physical disorders known as psychophysiological disorders.

Stress activates the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and sympathetic nervous system, leading to a decreased immune response, including reduced T-lymphocyte activity.

THREE DIMENSIONS OF PERSONALITY

Eysenck, Hans Jurgen 1916-97, was a british psychologist. He was known for his hypothesis of human character. He proposed that character not entirely settled and is organized in an order comprising of types, qualities, constant reactions, and explicit reactions. The three dimensions of personality is also called the PEN model.

P—Psychoticism versus impulse control E—Extraversion versus introversion N—Neuroticism versus emotional stability

PERSONALITY AND TEMPERAMENT

Gordon Allport defines personality as the dynamic organization of psychophysical systems within an individual, influencing their characteristic behaviour and thought. This definition acknowledges both biological and psychological factors, emphasizing the interaction between them. Personality evolves and develops while maintaining coherence, reflecting patterns of thoughts, feelings, emotions, and attitudes unique to each person.

HAHNEMANN'S VIEW OF PSYCHOSOMATIC DISEASES

Hahnemann placed significant emphasis on mental illnesses, viewing the mentally ill as whole individuals requiring appropriate care and treatment. In the *Organon*, sections §210 to §230 address mental disorders. Specifically, in §225, Hahnemann highlights psychosomatic diseases, noting that psychological factors such as prolonged anxiety, worry, stress, depression, and persistent fear can subtly affect the body or even have a significant physical impact. These mental conditions, he argued, can harm physical health.

In §226, Hahnemann explained that psychosomatic illnesses, which originate and persist due to mental influences, can be remedied through psychological interventions such as boosting self-confidence, offering friendly encouragement, giving advice, and, in some cases, using carefully planned deception. He also emphasized the importance of an appropriate diet and regimen in restoring health.

In §227, Hahnemann discussed the treatment of psychosomatic diseases, stating that the psoric miasm is the primary underlying cause, even before the disease fully develops. To prevent the progression of mental illness, he advised that patients should undergo antipsoric treatment as a precaution.

FEW PERSONALITY TRAITS OF LYCOPODIUM CLAVATUM

Anxiety	Sentimentality and soft heartedness
Egocentric	Senility and dementia
Bravado	Cowardice
Depression and despair	Self-esteem

FEW RUBRICS OF LYCOPODIUM MENTIONED IN VARIOUS REPERTORIES

- Kent: 'He has a fear that he will make mistakes
- Lack of confidence in his strength: Hahnemann, haughtiness- Boenninghausen
- Kent: Mildness
- Kent: Dictatorial
- Kent: Dreads the presence of new persons
- Kent: Fear of undertaking anything, Frightened at trifles

- Kent: Intolerant of contradiction
- Kent: Disposition to contradict
- Kent: Suicidal on waking
- Kent: Taciturn, Quarrelsome, Rudeness.
- Kent: Haughty

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY SETTING- The study was carried out in Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Medical Homoeopathic Hospital, Katraj, Pune. OPD and various camps are conducted by the hospital.

SELECTION OF SAMPLE- 30 cases, patients of both genders, fitting the inclusion and exclusion criteria are being considered for the research.

INCLUSION CRITERIA- Patients who's constitution fits into the picture of Lycopodium are taken into study. All the genders is involved in the study.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA- Individuals with emergency conditions like cardiovascular diseases, renal failure, liver failure and other risk factors are excluded from the study. Pregnant women and lactating women are excluded from study.

STUDY DESIGN- Non- Randomised study.

INTERVENTION-The drug which is included in the study is Lycopodium clavatum. This drug is given in different potencies according to the case and susceptibility of the patients. It was administered through oral route in the globule and powder form.

STASTISTICAL TECHNIQUE-Before and After results of EPQR-A questionnaire are taken. The response to the intervention, including the main complaints, overall well-being and improvement in condition, was evaluated using "The Outcome In relation to impact on Daily Living (ORIDL)".

DATA ANALYSIS- It was performed on the collected data using statistical computer software.

OUTCOME ASSESMENT- The study utilized the EPQR-A (Eysenck Personality Questionnaire-Revised) to measure personality traits before and after treatment. The descriptive statistics indicated a significant reduction in the mean EPQR-A score from 20.23 ± 1.04 before treatment to 13.06 ± 2.87 after treatment. The paired t-test yielded a T-statistic of 12.12 with a p-value of <0.001 , which is highly significant. With a p-value of 0.000^{***} , the T-statistic is 12.12 and is very significant. This result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, confirming that there is a significant difference in the EPQR-A scores before and after homoeopathic intervention. The substantial decrease in scores suggests that homoeopathic treatment effectively improves personality traits and associated diseases. The response to the intervention, including the main complaints, overall well-being and improvement in condition, was evaluated using "The Outcome In relation to impact on Daily Living (ORIDL)". The chi-square test further supports the study's findings by showing a statistically significant association between the improvement levels in EPQR-A scores and the overall improvement in patients' conditions. The chi-square test statistic of 28.894 with a p-value of <0.001 underscores the reliability of these results. Hence, we reject H_0 and conclude that there is as significant association between improvement levels of EPQR-A score and improvement in case(disease).

**RESULTS AND DISCUSSION-
DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION- DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS**

Figure 1: Pie diagram representing age wise distribution

Age	Number of patients	Percentage
18-22	2	6.67%
22-27	4	13.33%
27-32	15	50.00%
32-37	6	20.00%
above 37	3	10.00%

Table 1: Age wise distribution of patients

Table 1 and Figure 1 above demonstrate that in the study, 7% of patients were between the ages of 18 and 22; 13% were between the ages of 22 and 27; 50% were between the ages of 27 and 32; 20% were between the ages of 32 and 37; and 10% were over the age of 37.

Table 2: Gender-wise distribution of patients

Gender	No of Patients	Percentage
Female	13	43.33%
Male	17	56.67%

Figure 2: Distribution of patients according to Gender

Table 2 and Figure 2 present the patient distribution by gender. In the study, there were 43.33% female patients and 56.67% male patients.

Table 3: Potency-wise distribution of patients.

Remedy with potency	Number of patients	Percentage
Lycopodium Clavatum 1M	18	60.0%
Lycopodium Clavatum 200	12	40.0%

Figure 3: Distribution of patients according to potency.

Table no.3 and Figure 3 show the distribution of patients according to potency. 60% of patients were given Lycopodium Clavatum 1M, and the remaining 40% of patients were given Lycopodium Clavatum 200 in the study.

HYPOTHESIS TESTED:

H₀: The treatment of Lycopodium is not effective in the management of personality traits. Vs
H₁: The treatment of Lycopodium is effective in the management of personality traits.

Table 4: Paired t-test and Descriptive statistics of the EPQR-A Score before and after the intervention.

Score	N	Mean±SD	T Statistic Value	P-Value
before intervention	30	20.23±1.04	12.12	0.000***
after intervention	30	13.06±2.87		
Estimated difference:	7.16±3.23		95% CI for mean difference:	(5.95, 8.37)

P Value <0.001, which indicates a very significant statistical result. As a result, the EPQR-A score before and after differed significantly.

A test that was employed T Statistic-value: Test Statistic value; Paired t-test; ***: Highly Significant Difference.

95% CI for mean difference: 95% Confidence Interval for mean difference.

Table 4a: Descriptive statistics of the EPQR-A score before and after treatment.

EPQR-A	N	Mean±SD	Minimum	Maximum
Before treatment	30	20.23±1.04	18	22
After treatment	30	13.06±2.87	9	18

Figure 4: Bar diagram representing the Average ± SD of the EPQR-A score before and after the intervention.

Descriptive statistics and paired t-test findings of the EPQR-A score before and after the intervention are

displayed in Table 4, 4a, and Fig. 4. The score was 20.23±1.04 (mean + SD) prior to treatment, and it dropped to 13.06±2.87 following treatment.

The Paired t-test is used to examine the hypothesis of whether or not the average patient score stays the same before and after the intervention of homoeopathic medication.

With a p-value of 0.000 ***, the T-statistic is 12.12 and is very significant.

We find that there is a substantial difference between the average EPQR-A score before and

after the treatment, rejecting H_0 .

Personality traits can be effectively treated using homoeopathic drugs.

Table 5: Distribution of patients according to improvement in EPQR-A score after the intervention.

Improvement	Number of patients	Percentage
Good	17	56.67%
Moderate Improvement	8	26.67%
No Improvement	5	16.67%

Figure 5: Distribution of patients according to the improvement after intervention.

Table 5 and Figure 5 show the distribution of patients according to improvement in EPQR-A after intervention for personality traits.

56% of patients: Experienced significant improvement after treatment, with EPQR-A scores of 12 or below. 27% of patients: Showed a moderate level of improvement, corresponding to EPQR-A scores between 13 and 17.

17% of patients: Did not experience improvement after treatment for personality traits.

HYPOTHESIS TESTED:

H₀: There is no significant association between improvement levels of EPQR-A score and improvement in case (disease).

Vs

H₁: There is a significant association between improvement levels of EPQR-A score and improvement in case (disease).

The chi-square test was applied to test the hypothesis.

Assessment of response to previous intervention on main complaints as well as overall well being was made through “The Outcome in Relation to Impact on Daily Living (ORIDL).

Table 6: Improvement levels of EPQR-A and Improvement levels of The Case(disease).

	IMPROVEMENT CASE(ORIDL)	INIMPROVEMENT EPQR-A SCORE	IN
GOOD IMPROVEMENT	14	17	
MODERATE IMPROVEMENT	10	8	
NO IMPROVEMENT	6	5	

Table 6a: Chi-Square Tests

Test statistic	Value	df	p-value
Pearson Chi-Square	28.894	4	.000***
Likelihood Ratio	32.780	4	.000***

p-value*** <0.001, highly significant.

The chi-square test statistic value was 28.894 with a p-value < 0.001, statistically highly significant.

Hence, we reject Ho and conclude that there is a significant association between improvement levels of EPQR-A score and improvement in case (disease).

Figure 6: Distribution of improvement in case (disease) according to improvement level of EPQR-A
Figure 6 visually represents the Distribution of improvement in case (disease) according to the improvement level of EPQR-A.

Here, We reject Ho and conclude that there is a significant association between improvement levelsof EPQR-A score and improvement in case (disease).

The graph provides insights into the effectiveness of the EPQR-A assessment in predicting patient improvement.

CONCLUSION-

1. Study details-

30 patients treated over a period of 3 months.

Assessment done using EPQR-A and ORIDL before and after treatment.

2. Patient Demographics-

This study includes, 7% of patients were between the ages of 18 and 22, 13% were between the age of 22 and 27, 50% were between the ages of 27 and 32, 20% were between the age of 32 and 37, 10% were over age of 37.

In the study, there were 43.33% female patients and 56.67% male patients.

3. Potency wise distribution-

60% of patients were given Lycopodium Clavatum 1M, and the remaining 40% of patients were given Lycopodium Clavatum 200 in the study.

4. Treatment results-

56% of patients: Experienced significant improvement after treatment, with EPQR-A scores of 12 or below. 27% of patients showed a moderate level of improvement, corresponding to EPQR-A scores between 13 and 17. 17% of patients did not experience improvement after treatment.

5. Statistical Analysis- P Value <0.001, which indicates a very significant statistical result. As a result, the EPQR-A score before and after differed significantly.

A test that was employed T Statistic-value: Test Statistic value; Paired t-test; ***: Highly Significant Difference.

6. Conclusion- Lycopodium clavatum is effective in treating various diseases

LIMITATIONS- Included small sample size, short follow-up period, and lack of a control group. The study suggests potential for homeopathic treatment in migraine management, but larger studies are needed for more conclusive results.

REFERENCES-

1. Hahnemann S, Dudgeon RE, translators. Organon of Medicine. 6th ed. New Delhi: B.Jain Publishers; 2005.
2. Samaran R, Vivek R. Concept of psychosomatic disorders in homeopathy: A review. Int J Homoeopathic Sci. 2020;4(2):150-155.
3. Matthews G, Deary IJ, Whiteman MC. Personality Traits. 3rd ed. New York: Cambridge University Press; 2009.
4. Ryckman R. Theories of Personality. 9th ed. Belmont: Cengage Learning; 2007. Hall CS. Theories of Personality. 2nd ed.
5. Matthews G, Gilliland K. The personality theories of H. J. Eysenck and J. A. Gray: A comparative review. Personality and Individual Differences. 1999;26:583-626.
6. Nolen-Hoeksema S, Fredrickson BL, Loftus GR, Wagenaar WA. Atkinson & Hilgard's Introduction to Psychology. 15th ed. Andover: Cengage Learning EMEA; 2009.
7. Allen JH. The Chronic Miasms, Psora, Pseudo and Sycosis. Indian Books and Periodicals Publishers; 2006.
8. Chatterjee A, Shah KB, Joshi N, Lathiya R, Panda BP. Understanding temperament- through a retrospective study of randomly selected chronic case. Int J Homoeopathic Sci. 2021;5(3):147-157.
9. Kaur S. A Concise Textbook of Human Psychology. 1st ed. New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers; 2008.
10. Review of Lycopodium clavatum with homeopathic perspective and modern pharmacology. World J Pharm Res. 2018;7(12):182-187.
11. Homeopathic Pharmacopoeia of India Revised and Augmented. 2016.
12. Sayre LE. A Manual of Organic Materia Medica and Pharmacognosy. Philadelphia: P. Blakiston's Son; 1900. Digitized 2008 Jan 29. Available from: Harvard University.

13. Wang B, Guan C, Fu Q. The traditional uses, secondary metabolites, and pharmacology of Lycopodium species. *Phytochem Rev.* 2022;21:1-79.
14. Bailey PM. *Homeopathic Psychology: Personality Profiles of the Major Constitutional Remedies.* 1995.
15. Farrington EA. *Lectures on Clinical Materia Medica.* New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers Pvt. Limited; 2003.
16. Hahnemann S. *The Chronic Diseases.* Philadelphia: Boericke & Tafel; 1896.
17. Allen TF, editor. *The Encyclopedia of Pure Materia Medica: A Record of the Positive Effects of Drugs Upon the Healthy Human Organism.* Vol. 7. Philadelphia: Boericke & Tafel; 1878.
18. Hahnemann S. *The Chronic Diseases: Their Peculiar Nature and Their Homoeopathic Cure.* New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers; 1999.
19. Kent JT. *Lectures on Homoeopathic Materia Medica: Together with Kent's "New Remedies" Incorporated and Arranged in One Alphabetical Order.* New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers Pvt. Limited; 1998.
20. Boericke W. *Pocket Manual of Homoeopathic Materia Medica & Repertory.* New Delhi: Kuldeep Jain for B. Jain Publishers; 2002.
21. Nash EB. *Regional Leaders.* New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers Pvt. Limited; 2003.
22. Nash EB. *Leaders in Homoeopathic Therapeutics.* B. Jain Publishers Pvt. Limited; 2002.
23. Vithoukas G. *The Essence of Materia Medica.* New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers (P) Limited; 2009.
24. Tyler ML. *Homoeopathic Drug Pictures.* New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers; 1990.
25. Hering C. *Guiding Symptoms of Our Materia Medica.* 10th ed. New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers Pvt. Limited; 2005.
26. Dimopoulou C, Ising M, Pfister H, Schopohl J, Stalla GK, Sievers C. Increased Prevalence of Anxiety-Associated Personality Traits in Patients with Cushing's Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Neuroendocrinology.* 2013;97(2):139-145.
27. Brickman AL, Yount SE, Blaney NT, Rothberg ST, Kaplan De-Nour A. Personality Traits and Long-Term Health: The Influence of Neuroticism and Conscientiousness on Renal Deterioration in Type-1 Diabetes. *Psychosomatics.* 1996;37(5):459-468.
28. Prince EJ, Siegel DJ, Carroll CP, Sher KJ, Bienvenu OJ. A longitudinal study of personality traits, anxiety, and depressive disorders in young adults. *Anxiety Stress Coping.* 2020.
29. Ma C, Kang J, Xu T. The impact of personality traits on pessary treatment outcomes in patients with pelvic organ prolapse. *Int Urogynecol J.* 2021;32:859-864.
30. Sieurin J, Gustavsson P, Weibull CE, Feldman AL, Petzinger GM, Gatz M, Pedersen NL, Wirdefeldt K. Personality traits and the risk for Parkinson disease: a prospective study. *Eur J Epidemiol.* 2016;31(2):169-175.
31. Buckley L, MacHale SM, Cavanagh JTO, Sharpe M, Deary IJ, Lawrie SM. Personality dimensions in chronic fatigue syndrome and depression. *J Psychosom Res.* 1999;46(4):395-400.
32. Kazgan Kılıçaslan A, Yıldız S, Kurt O, Atmaca M. Personality characteristics, anxiety sensitivity, anxiety, and depression levels in patients diagnosed with psychogenic pruritus. *Alpha Psychiatry.* 2022;23(5):243-252.
33. Roy A. Neuroticism and depression in alcoholics. *J Affect Disord.* 1999;52(1-3):243-245.
34. Bhalerao R, Oberai P, Mehra P, Rai Y, Choubey G, Sahoo AR, et al. Lycopodium clavatum for the management of urolithiasis: A randomised double blind placebo controlled trial. *Indian J Res Homoeopathy.* 2019;13:139-49.
35. Dr. Mehadi Arif Billah, Dr. Abdul Hakim SK, Dr. Vignesh Kumar S, Dr. Syed Afsar Ali, Dr. Subhashis Pramanik. A case report of left sided ureteric calculus cured by lycopodium clavum in Im potency. *Int J Hom Sci* 2022;6(4):494-498.
36. Kanwar A, Ram H, Kumar N, Bagdi N. Plaque Psoriasis Successfully Treated with an Individualised Homoeopathic Medicine Lycopodium: A Case Report. *Thieme Med Sci Publ Pvt Ltd.* DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0040-1714381>.
37. Bala R, Srivastava A, Chingakhm R. Importance of mental symptoms in homoeopathy: A case report on vitiligo. *Int J Homoeopathic Sci.* 2020;4(1):124-130.

38. Nath A, Palit DK, Kundu N. Homoeopathic management of ovarian cyst – a case report. An International Journal of Research in AYUSH and Allied Systems.
39. Arya B, Nagar P, Mahiya S, Choudhary G, Kumar D. Clinical verification of individualized Homoeopathic medicine Lycopodium in Diabetes mellitus: A case study. Int J Homoeopathic Sci. 2021;5(2):95-104.
40. Hossain A. The Prescription on Mind Symptoms. Homœopathic Links. 2015;28(1):39- 43.
41. Samaran R, Vivek R. Concept of psychosomatic disorders in homoeopathy: A review. Int J Homoeopathic Sci. 2020;4(2):150-155.
42. Yaralagadda U, Dolas VV. Homoeopathic preparation of Lycopodium clavatum emphasizing the importance of mental symptoms on different diseases - a systematic review. J Nonlinear Anal Optim. 2024;15(1):2.